

CASE STUDY

FAIRplus use case IMI ELF:

FAIR data sharing in early drug discovery partnerships

Jan-Willem Boiten, Daniela Bonora, Erwin Boutsma, Ilse Custers, Alexander Duyndam, Yojana Gadiya, Phil Gribbon, Nick Juty

Challenge

A chemical library, built within the IMI-funded ELF project, was designed to be easily shared between the ELF partners, selected academics and small and medium-sized biotech companies throughout Europe. The library consists of over 535,000 compounds that can serve as starting points for the development of new small molecule therapeutics. A FAIRplus squad team, consisting of members of both the ELF and FAIRplus projects, was tasked with investigating what would be necessary to make this unique ELF resource more FAIR, thus making it more valuable for others if and when the compound library is made available to the wider scientific community.

Background

The [European Lead Factory \(ELF\)](#)¹ is a pan-European public-private partnership established in 2013 and funded by the Innovative Medicines Initiative (IMI). It developed infrastructure and expertise for research teams to perform high-throughput screens to investigate which chemical compounds work best on specified drug targets. The first phase of the project ran until 2018, as a consortium in which several pharmaceutical companies, universities, and small- and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) joined forces to create a high-quality compound library as well as a screening infrastructure referred to as the European Screening Centre. The goal of the project was to boost early drug discovery by seeding lead finding programmes with high quality hit validated compounds.

From 2019, the ELF continued under a second round of IMI-funding, known as [ESCulab](#)². This second phase has built on the achievements of ELF1 and runs until November 2023. The recruitment phase of the project has now closed, but until recently, researchers with drug targets could apply to have their target screened against the ELF compound library and receive help in further optimising any resulting hits.

'The ELF partnership has already run over 250 high-throughput screens on actual drug targets', current ELF Coordinator and Lygature's Strategy Director Jon de Vlieger explains. 'Each of these screens resulted in valuable data on the compounds screened and their behaviour in a specific biological setting. It's a unique dataset found nowhere else in the world.' Until recently, access to the collection and screening infrastructure was only available for European-based organisations, but the ELF has now also launched a [worldwide partnering program for charities and non-profits](#)³.

Working across the IMI project portfolio, the IMI [FAIRplus](#)⁴ project aims to develop tools and guidelines for making life science data FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). In the past years, squad teams from FAIRplus, consisting of experts working in universities and pharmaceutical companies, have been actively working to FAIRify data resources from collaborating IMI projects, such as [APPROACH](#)⁵, [COMBINE](#)⁶, and [ELF](#) (including [ESCulab](#)). The developed tools and methods are subsequently added as 'recipes' to the [FAIR Cookbook](#), enabling projects and companies with similar FAIR data challenges to apply this consolidated know-how to increase the FAIRness of their data and data management processes.

1. <https://www.europeanleadfactory.eu/>

2. <https://www.imi.europa.eu/projects-results/project-factsheets/esculab>

3. <https://www.europeanleadfactory.eu/partnering-opportunities-charities-foundations>

4. <https://www.imi.europa.eu/projects-results/project-factsheets/fairplus>

5. <https://www.imi.europa.eu/projects-results/project-factsheets/approach>

6. <https://www.imi.europa.eu/projects-results/project-factsheets/combine>

Results

In September 2022, the FAIRplus squad team assessed the FAIR maturity level of the ELF dataset during a three-day meeting with the ELF team. They found an extensive, already well-structured database built over a period of ten years. 'The main operational goal of the ELF when working with individual project teams has been to narrow a list of compounds of interest from over 535,000 to the best 50', Herman van Vlijmen, involved in both the ELF and FAIRplus projects, explains. 'This means you need to structure the database and optimize it for handling the volumes of data coming from high-throughput screening.'

In addition, in the early stages of the ELF, a user-oriented system known as the Honest Data Broker (HDB) was developed to handle access rights, legal and IP issues, etc, making the sharing of data across consortium members relatively straightforward. 'Our HDB was built before the FAIR principles were developed, but since it works with a highly structured and standardised dataset, there's a clear path forward for FAIRifying the HDB system and the data it contains', said Jason Swedlow, ELF's HDB work package lead from the University of Dundee's School of Life Sciences and National Phenotypic Screening Centre.

Still, the FAIR squad team found some room for improvement in the metadata representation, especially when considering the future possibility of sharing data outside of the consortium. Although it is currently not within the scope of the ELF to make datasets openly available outside the partnership, Van Vlijmen doesn't rule out that this might happen in the future. The FAIRplus squad team, therefore, recommended the metadata be enriched. Phil Gribbon, FAIRplus work package lead, explains: 'Within the consortium, there was a certain logic to the metadata, but to link it to datasets outside the consortium would be a challenge. For example, the ELF identifies proteins in the database with a UniProt ID, but these weren't linked to the online [UniProt resource](#)⁷.'

The FAIRplus squad team's recommendations are also going to be used as input for a future strategy, De Vlieger states. 'We are implementing the quick wins in our current database. Some were even implemented already during the three-day meeting with the squad team. For follow-up projects, we will build upon these recommendations and implement them from the start, since we realize this will likely save us a lot of time.'

The benefit

FAIRifying the ELF dataset is useful for current research projects, but De Vlieger stresses that the real benefit lies in the future. 'I believe the most important aspect is that we secure the value of the dataset beyond the current funding term. The investment in generating the dataset is huge. It seems only logical that, many years from now, the data is still findable, accessible, and usable to serve the overall goal of early drug discovery projects like the ELF.'

7. <https://www.uniprot.org/>